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China's Pivot to Central Asia: Sino-Russian Strategic Partnership or Asymmetrical Relations?

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Abstract: *China and Russia developed their strategic relations by limiting the United States' role as a global power and by a desire to create a multipolar world. The international political and economic scenario brought both countries close to each other. In the post-Cold War era, the resolution of border issues between Russia and China initiated the era of normalization in their ties. The establishment of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) was a landmark initiative for bringing together the major states of Asia towards strategic cooperation. SCO is based on collaboration on economic and security cooperation among member states. The US launched 'the War on Terror' in 2001, and its presence in Afghanistan raised mutual security concerns, and both Russia and China realized the need for cooperation in the region. In 2014, Russian relations with the West collapsed over the Ukrainian crisis, deepening Sino-Russian relations and paving the way for Russia's pivot towards Asia. The nature of the Sino-Russian relationship is not as simple as both states' economic and political interests are competitive. The bilateral relations between countries are a product of Western policies and also based on the basis of their interests in Central Asia. Apart from China and Russia, Central Asia has remained the focus of attention for Asian and Western powers for its intact hydrocarbon reserves and trade potential. Central Asia has an 'International Security Dynamics', involving the powers in a complex competition. Currently, Sino-Russian relations are a mixture of competitive cooperation. On one side, China's growing security role and the initiative of the BRI with the Central Asian states can create asymmetry, while the ambition of making a multipolar world and a collective response towards Western strategies brings accommodating behavior in their policies.*

Keywords: *China and Russia developed their strategic relations by limiting the United States' role as a global power and by a desire to create a multipolar world. The international political and economic scenario brought both countries close to each other. In the post-Cold War era, the resolution of border issues*

Introduction

In recent years, the Sino-Russian strategic partnership has taken a turn and developed into a more engaging and deepening partnership for a mutual cause. The desire behind this robust cooperation is to bring the world towards a multipolar world order where the influence of the West and the United States could be checked. Throughout the Cold War era, the Soviet Union was the sole key player in the region. Even after the disintegration of the Soviet Union, Russia enjoyed its influential status, but after the Crimean Crisis and the Ukraine War, it is tolerating Chinese influence in Central Asia. Both countries are cooperating closely in various fields. But China's excessive influence in Central Asia, particularly in security, economics, and technology sectors in the 'strategic backyard' of Russia, is causing asymmetry in their relations. The study investigates whether prospects of mutual interests in the region

and beyond are more valuable for states to avoid this asymmetry or can create a rift between Asian major powers. From 1996 to 2011, their relations continued to grow and were converted into a “Comprehensive Strategic and Cooperative Partnership”. Apart from Russia, in recent years, China’s influence in Central Asia has been swift, and its rise as an economic superpower in the region has created a paradox in the relations between the two states. China solidified its position in Central Asia economically. China’s emerging posture is bothering Russia to some extent, but the common interest of balancing with the West and the United States’ keeping their close alliance intact, regardless of their competitive interests in the commerce and trade sectors. Historically, the region of Central Asia has been a strategic realm for the major powers of the world for its geopolitical and economic significance. Among these major powers, Russia has successfully dominated the region for several decades. China’s entry into the region brought a decisive shift by replacing the conventional role of Russia gradually. So, there is a dynamic interplay of economic and security interests between Russia and China that is shaping their evolving relationship in Central Asia. Strategically, Central Asia occupies a unique place in international history for economic and security considerations. This region is situated at the crossroads of invaders and traders. Geographically, it is located in a significant area of Asia, which is considered the basis of controlling world politics by political geographers. Its territory is expanding from China in the east and in the west to the Caspian Sea, from Russia to Afghanistan in the north, and Iran in the south. In ancient times, the traditional Silk Route, which passes through Central Asia, was a connecting point for global trade. Its geographical location and intact energy resources have served as a strategic bridge connecting the East and West and North and South. Owing to its immense vital location and energy reservoirs, it is gaining the attention of major powers.

Evolution of Russia-Central Asia Relations: A Historical Perspective

Geographically, Russia’s 75 % territory lies in Asia and 25 % in Europe, so it has always been a major power of both Europe and Asia. Its strategic location in Asia grants it an imperial outlook for Central Asia. Geopolitically, Russia has always been more powerful than the Central Asian states, and Russia treated the Central Asian states as a colonizer, but it was a brief period. This colonialism started in the 18th century in some northern areas of Kazakhstan and lasted in the region until the 19th century. The nature of their relationship is very complex; on one side, it is a colonizer-colonial type, while on the other side, it is also symbolized as a cohabitation of Russo-Central Asia because of having the same civilization. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, it was difficult for Moscow to keep its strong presence in the region (Laruelle, 2009). Initially, Russia didn’t show any interest in the Central Asian states, which formed the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS). In the era of Vladimir Putin, Russia took the initiative to secure its vital interests in the former Soviet space by visiting Uzbekistan and Tajikistan in 2000. Russia revised its policy by channeling diplomatic practices and launching several investment projects in Central Asian states. Russia, in joint ventures with strategic partners Iran, India, and China, promoted enormous economic activity in Central Asian states. From 2000 to 2008, Putin succeeded in securing Russia’s position as the largest strategic partner in Central Asia both bilaterally and multilaterally. On a bilateral level, Russia is a strategic and military ally of the region, and on a multilateral level, Russia successfully concluded two crucial platforms for security and the economy: The Eurasian Economic Community and the Collective Security Treaty in 2000 and 2002, respectively. Russia also serves as the basic political model for Central Asian states, which are not fascinated by the Chinese monopartite system or the Western parliamentary systems. During the Putin era, Russia correctly articulated the differences between Western and Central Asian states on the mode of authoritarian regimes in CIS countries. So, it successfully contained the Western ideology in the region. Besides politics, Russia dominated the economic sectors of the Central Asian states. Russia’s main focus has been on hydrocarbon resources. The energy supplies from Central Asia to Russia are unidirectional. Central Asia exports hydrocarbons to Russia, and Russia makes minimal use of these products and re-exports to Europe. Since the collapse of the Soviet Union, the region of Central Asia has been in a phase of transformation, but in certain areas, Central Asian states are dependent on Russia. After the disintegration of the Soviet Union, Central Asian states remained under the strong influence of Russia in economic, political, and security spheres. Russia has been assisting the Central Asian states in their security and economic sectors. The Collective Security Treaty Organization (CSTO) and the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) have been crucial instruments that enabled Moscow to control the Central Asian region through modernizing its armed forces and providing assistance in economic sectors. This scenario shows that after the Cold War era, losing direct control over Central Asia, Russia retained its influence in the region. Historical examination and current recalibration of Russia with the

Central Asian states manifest that it was not inclined towards Central Asia based on Western alienation after the Ukraine crisis. Instead, a deliberate policy owing to long-term vested interests in the region (Wong, 2023, pp. 287-300).

Research Methodology

This paper investigates the impact of China's growing security role in Central Asia and its impact on the competitive strategies of China and Russia in the region through qualitative research methodology. The data collected through scholarly articles, documents, and books points out China's security and economic strategies in the Eurasian region and their concurrent implications. Their bilateral agreements, policy documents, and official statements give a sketch of Chinese development and its increasing stakes. The comparative analysis of policy actions and their impacts provides a contextual understanding of complementarities and highlights asymmetries in the approaches of both states.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework in this study suggests that realism comprehensively explains the importance of strategic interests and the role of power in international relations. According to the realist school of thought, ensuring security and seeking power is the primary objective of a state. In the case of China and Russia, their competitive and cooperative actions in the region help to understand their efforts to secure maximum influence in Central Asian states. To understand the behaviors of Russia and China as power-seeking states in Central Asia, neorealism provides a structural understanding by pointing out the constraints and opportunities for Russia and China to gain influence. Neorealism focuses on the self-help strategies of a state to ensure security and secure maximum power for its survival in an anarchic international structure. Moreover, neorealism also focuses on the personal gain of a state rather than mutual prospects (Waltz, 1979). In this scenario, Sino-Russian bilateral interaction in Central Asia is a matter of concern, yet their strategies vis-à-vis the United States are also the subject matter of this study, as both states are not happy with a US-led global order. So, the Sino-Russian strategic equation not only demands balancing against each other in the region but also their balancing approach against the United States globally (PİRİ, 2023).

Sino-Russian Bilateral Relations in the 21st Century

Sino-Russian Bilateral Relations in the 21st Century cannot be characterized as friendly throughout the Cold War era, but with the dawn of the 21st century, three important factors brought both states toward developing close ties. Firstly, both countries have a common positioning against the United States. Secondly, to compete and revise the international order led by the United States and the West. Thirdly, the international security environment and the security challenges, particularly in Central Asia. As far as their bilateral relations are concerned, Sino-Russian cooperation is widespread across politics, economy, energy, and security. Russia is the main source of energy supplies and raw materials to China, and China, in return, ensures its access to Russian markets. Both countries are jointly working on the security of Asia, and China is also interested in getting access to Europe through Russia. Russia has been assisting China in modernizing its military capability and the army (Li & Poh, 2019, pp. 21-39). Viewing China's rise in Central Asia is not acceptable for Russia, but it has to be cautious in opposing the Chinese initiatives directly; instead, Russia is accommodating itself with the maximum possible collaboration, particularly under the framework of the SCO. It is a fact that with the pace at which China's influence is expanding in Central Asia, Russia is incapable of matching it. So, the asymmetry between Russia and China is a reality and essential. However, the nature of Sino-Russian relations is not a zero-sum rivalry, but rather a collaborative competition. China is interested in increasing its economic influence through connectivity projects, and Russia is concerned about maintaining its leading security role in the region. There is a central question on Russia's exclusiveness with China in Asia, where there are other Asian powers too, such as Japan. Wong justifies the pivot of China based on geopolitical facts and regional limitations. By viewing the alignment policy in Asia, Japan looks institutionally and ideologically more pro-West than China. Strategically, the Sino-Russia nexus is creating a Eurasian continental alignment, while the US-Japan collaboration is an Indo-Pacific maritime alignment. The former is linked with 'Heartland,' and the latter is associated with 'Rimland,' geopolitics, respectively. Even though Russia tolerates China's economic and security expansion in Central Asia, overall, the true nature of their relations is not considered a partnership, as it has tilted towards an

increasingly asymmetrical relationship. After the Crimean crisis of 2014 and particularly the Ukraine war of 2022, China is serving as a crucial economic 'lifeline' for Russia. Western Europe and the United States used instruments of statecraft such as Society for Worldwide Interbank Financial Telecommunication (SWIFT) and the oil price caps to isolate Russia financially (Wong, 2023, pp. 310-314)

China's Connectivity Projects in Central Asia and Russia's Response

China's economic ambitions, particularly through connectivity and infrastructure projects, are the top priority of its strategic policy. China sees Central Asia as a 'transit corridor' to Europe. Central Asia is one of the most disconnected regions in the world. In Central Asia, conflicts, contradictions, and internal problems among states kept them from engaging economically and politically. The Belt and Road Initiative promises opportunities for local actors to change their previous approach. Since the announcement of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) by the Chinese President in 2013, it has been the most crucial concern for international politics, but exclusively for Central Asia and Russia. BRI is a large-scale, unique project that links China to the rest of the world, comprising 60 countries, for commercial purposes through huge continental and maritime infrastructure. BRI is also considered China's peaceful and multilateral response to the United States' new Asia-Pacific strategy. BRI, several Chinese energy and infrastructure projects, maritime strategy, and the establishment of ports are collectively named the Chinese paradigm: the rise of China through soft power. China's connectivity plan comprises more than 100 large-scale and small-scale infrastructure projects in its access to Europe through Central Asia and Russia. China wants to attract more SCO countries to these initiatives, and the BRI will help China gain access to Europe. Five Central Asian countries are a focus of the BRI project, which are Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Uzbekistan. Currently, Chinese goods are transported through the Suez Canal, which takes a long time, and through Central Asia. There are two ways by which Chinese goods could get entry into Europe in a short span of time: one through Russia and the other through Kazakhstan. For this huge project, China pledged to assist Central Asian Countries in two ways: through the funds of the Silk Road Foundation and the Asian Infrastructure Bank (AIIB), US 40 billion and US\$100 billion, respectively. China will also provide aid to the participants of the project. Through BRI, China is becoming the largest investor in the region.

Chinese interests and its economic expansion in Central Asia are a matter of concern for Russia, which is the dominant key player of the region in all respects. Central Asia is a special zone of Russia's national interest and China's growing influence, posing security challenges to the bilateral relations of China and Russia. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, the Central Asian countries remained largely dependent on Russia for the safety of their prime objectives: economic, security, and politics. Russia is so concerned about its key role towards Central Asia that after the implication of BRI by China, its influence is being challenged, and there is a transformation in Central Asian countries in how they see China for their economic and security considerations as an alternative to Russia. Chinese efforts are bringing a change with its conception of locals, but Russia has an edge in its sociocultural impact on the region. Though mutual concern of Sino-Russia consolidated relations is stronger to keep their relations cordial against the United States' dominant posture in the region, Russia also wants to curb China's increasing economic power by inviting India for trade with the Central Asian countries. Initially, Russia's strategy to balance China in the region is manifested by its following actions:

- Russian efforts to make India a permanent member of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), which China accepted in view of making Pakistan also a permanent member of SCO. Both countries got their permanent membership in 2017.
- Secondly, Russia is also working for a free trade agreement between EAEU and India so that the Central Asian region cannot turn into a Chinese landscape; it is also willing to conclude a free trade agreement between the Eurasia Economic Union (EAEU) and India by 2020.
- For India, there is an opportunity to expand its area of influence and to contain China, which is its supreme foreign policy goal. Russia wants to maintain the relations between China and the Central Asian countries according to its framework in 2015.

In a joint declaration, Russia announced unilaterally a cooperative mechanism with China to combine the projects of EAEU and BRI so that their objectives could be supplemented. Russia's move raised

suspicion in Central Asian countries that they do not want to work in the Russian framework because Central Asia is not a politically unified area. Since the inception of Central Asian countries in 1991, though having independence and sovereignty, Central Asian countries are largely dependent on Russia for security, economic, and cultural objectives. CARs are struggling to de-Russianize themselves. Meanwhile, Chinese economic initiatives are providing them with an opportunity to gain their national identity and an alternative to Russia. Russia is quite aware that China's increasing ties could damage its longstanding involvement in the region. Therefore, it is warmly welcoming India into the region to initiate a multiplayer game. Even though Russia also knows that Central Asian countries could bypass the EAEU platform and develop bilateral economic ties with India, it is acceptable to extend bilateral relations with India rather than to convert this region into a Chinese economic and political panorama (Jiang, 2020).

- Besides India, Russia is looking towards more allies to keep the balance against China. Japan and Germany are other options to play to accommodate Moscow against Beijing.
- Russia is also concerned to end its aloofness with the West and has also called upon America for better relations.
- Russia wants to curb Chinese influence in the region diplomatically, not in a hostile way. Russia's reservations are based on the apprehensions of becoming China's 'Junior Partner' in the region.

Latest Trends in Sino-Russia Relations from the Perspective of Central Asia

China is contributing in various sectors of Central Asia and strengthening its deep ties in the region in following areas;

China's Economic Relations with Central Asian States: In recent years, China's posture in Central Asia emerged as a primary trading partner, replacing Russia's long-term dominance in the region. China's trading engagements with the states of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan reached \$ 106.3 billion from 2024 to 2026. China's exports to the region are of \$ 71.2 billion, consisting of high-tech goods, machinery, and electronics. Imports are of \$ 35.1 billion from Central Asia, and these consist of energy, minerals, and agricultural products. This trade structure shows China's consolidated position in the region as the primary trading power, leaving Russia behind (The Times of Central Asia , 2026).

Sino-Central Asia Security Relations

In connecting projects, China is working on building a "middle corridor" with the milestone project of the China-Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan (CKU) railway. It is a crucial link connecting Europe, bypassing Russia. This critical link will provide the Central Asian states with strategic diversification by reducing their dependency on Russian transit routes (Assylkhano, 2025, pp. 7-8).

In the security sector, China is working on counter terrorism and law enforcement development with the Central Asian states beyond the scope of the SCO. It will strengthen its security relations with the region. The Astana Summit 2025 in Kazakhstan is a manifestation of China's increasing security engagements in the region. The Ukraine war has also provided the opportunity for China to enhance its influence in the security sector to address the increasing security demands of the region. As Tajikistan is receiving Chinese assistance in border management and anti-terrorism training, where previously Russia was engaged. Viewing this Chinese increasing engagement in the region, Russia introduced a new Collective Security Treaty Organization (CSTO) Doctrine in January 2026 (Apostolov, 2026, pp. 239-252). This is a strategic step taken by Russia to keep its relevance in the region in the security sphere by focusing on 'Military Modernization' and a new 'Eurasian Security Architecture'. So, Sino-Russian relations in the region are characterized as competitive, where Russia is concerned to play the role of net security provider of the region, but largely depends on Chinese investment.

Sino-Central Asia Strategic Relations

There is a strategic outlook of Sino-Central Asian relations. Central Asia not only serves China as a resource hub but also as a strategic mirror. It is proving to be a testing ground for its economic integration and connectivity initiatives before applying worldwide. The BRI and the international security models can

be trialed in the region to check the flaws and effectiveness before launching them on a larger scale. China is carefully expanding its posture beyond a financial investor to a strategic partner of Central Asian states without challenging the Russian ego. On the other hand, Russia is accepting this new reality with a pragmatic restraint policy and trying to remain relevant by creating leverage on CSTO. So, this is a tectonic shift in the region on behalf of China to increase its zone of influence in the backyard of Russia owing to the international scenario after 2014 and the crisis of 2022 in the region (Zhang, 2024, pp. 1-16).

Conclusion:

Both China and Russia see Central Asia as an integral part of their long-term strategies of maintaining stability and development, conserving the intact resources of this region against the United States and Western countries. China is actively engaging in the region and making its presence stronger to cope with the targets of its internal development. There are three crucial interests of China for continued attention towards this region: security, stability, and integration with the Eurasian region for expansion of its markets by building overland routes such as BRI. China's resource investment in Central Asia has the potential for tensions between China and Russia. Russia, through its Eurasian Economic Union (EEU), and China, through BRI, are trying to increase their influence in the region, but China is getting the advantage. Even though both countries showed their desire to co-exist, these two platforms, the BRI, have the potential to eclipse EEU, and in the long run could decrease the dependence of China on Russia. China's increasing ties with enriched hydrocarbon Central Asian countries will serve as an alternative for Chinese energy imports. Currently, China is dependent on Russia for its energy supplies, and it imports 14 % of its crude oil from Russia. Russia wants to maintain its leverage and clout as a stabilizing power in the region. It has a strong military presence through troops and military deployments all over the region, and it is also a large exporter of arms, but economic distress in Russia is limiting its military influence. While China is also working to enhance its security posture in the region through its military overseas, and in the coming years, Russia's military advantage could be minimized by China as it is investing in the security sector. Over the past few years, China has increased its arms exports to Central Asia by 18 percent. China also established its first military facility in Tajikistan. Since 2000, Chinese military exports to Central Asia have reached to \$ 444 million, and launched several military exercises in the region. But still, Russia is dominating the region in the security sector (Sahai, 2019).

In the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, 'Virus Diplomacy' was initiated by major powers, including the USA, the European Union, India, and China. In actuality, China was the primary initiator of virus diplomacy, followed by other powers later. China assisted the Central Asian countries with the vaccine and other medical supplies. In its effort to provide health aid, China donated a plane carrying 500 kg of testing kits and PPE equipment to Kazakhstan in April 2020. In the same month, a medical team and 17000 test kits were provided to Kyrgyzstan and 2000 to Tajikistan (Jardine & Lemon, 2020). Sino-Russian policies are an example of mutual tolerance despite having political and ideological differences in the region. Yet, this coexistence policy is more helpful for China because China is significantly increasing its security role in the region. Bilateral ties between China and Central Asian Countries are getting strengthened in various fields, particularly in political and economic spheres. In the dyadic relations of Russia and China, the power gap is visible while working together, where Russia is struggling to maintain its influence, and China is emerging as a competitor with an edge in power and economic structure. Yet, Sino-Russian coexistence is more helpful for China because China is dramatically increasing its security role in the region. Bilateral ties between China and Central Asian Countries are getting strengthened. There is a difference in the posture of both states while working together, where Russia is struggling to maintain its influence and China is emerging as a competitor. Russia's position is more challenging with a downfall in the economy and also in demography, and it will have serious geopolitical consequences. Yet, Central Asia offers several regional and sub-regional arrangements to balance the Sino-Russian duopoly.

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